

Title: The Blockchain Technology – Fintech & Beyond

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INTRODUCTION:

Cryptocurrencies, especially Bitcoins and Ethereum, have hit the headlines many times over the years, but it is still unclear for the masses, and even among what is exactly the technology behind it, how it works

Introduce the basis of the Blockchain technology to the audience, present its major use cases in Fintech and beyond.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This presentation results in several hours of deep and methodological researches over the past 8 months, as well as experimentations conducted with a team of ICT professionals on Frameworks like the open source, enterprise-ready Blockchain Technology platform **Openchain** or the Microsoft open source platform **Coco**.

RESULTS:

A comprehensive introduction to the Blockchain will be available, as well as proof of concept projects based on the Technology.

CONCLUSIONS:

The cryptocurrencies have really helped uncovering the high potential of the Blockchain Technology on a very large scale. Still it is not widely used yet for other purposes.

Blockchain could be a factor in the next technological revolution that might have a bigger impact than the Internet revolution, therefore it is important to be informed.

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain, Fintech, Proof of Concept, POC, Proof of Work, POF, Bitcoin, Ethereum, openchain, coco, cryptocurrencies

BIOGRAPHY:

Adou SOW has an Engineer degree in the Management of Information Technology and is actually following a MBA in Investment and Corporate Business Administration.

After participating to and managing software development projects during several years, he successfully contributed in the launch of a commercial bank's branch in Senegal as the IT Manager, by defining and leading the implementation of the ICT Operations.

He is now an independent ICT Consultant, specialized in Projects, Processes and Quality Management, who has recently decided to get more involved in Fintech and study the Blockchain Technology.